

Thione or Thiol: Structural Confirmation of (E)-2-(1-(4-cyanophenyl)ethylidene)-N-(2-fluoro-4-sulfamoylphenyl)hydrazine-1-Carbothioamide and Carbonic Anhydrase Inhibition Studies

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Abstract

Thiosemicarbazones are Schiff bases formed by condensing an aldehyde or ketone with thiosemicarbazide derivatives. TSCs exhibit various biological activities and act as precursors for key scaffolds, with keto-enol tautomerism commonly resulting in thione or thiol forms. This study focuses on synthesizing and confirming the structure of compound **1**, (E)-2-(1-(4-cyanophenyl)ethylidene)-N-(2-fluoro-4-sulfamoylphenyl)hydrazine-1-carbothioamide, through a condensation reaction in methanol. Both theoretical and experimental IR and X-ray studies confirm the presence of the thione form and E isomerism. Compound **1** showed inhibitory activity against four human carbonic anhydrase isoforms (hCA I, II, IX, XII) with K_i values of 36.0, 5.7, 29.5, and 7.0 nM, respectively.

Keywords: thiosemicarbazone, synthesis, tautomerism, carbonic anhydrase, x-ray, docking

Introduction

Thiosemicarbazones (TSC) are Schiff bases that are prepared from the condensation of an aldehyde or ketone with thiosemicarbazide derivatives. TSCs have a variety of biological activities and serve as a precursor for essential scaffolds. The keto-enol tautomerism is one of the most common phenomena observed in TSCs, making them present either in thione or thiol form (Scheme 1)[1].

Scheme 1. Tautomerism of thiosemicarbazones

Carbonic anhydrases (CAs) are metal-containing enzymes that are identified in almost all organisms and catalyze an essential physiological reaction that involves the interconversion of CO_2 and HCO_3^- . They are structurally categorized into eight independent families, which are the alpha (α), beta (β), gamma (γ), delta (δ), zeta (ζ), eta (η), theta (θ), and (iota) ι CAs. To date, 15 α -CA (hCA) isoenzymes have been identified in humans and abnormal or (over)expression of hCA are mostly associated with the development and progression of several pathological disorders [2,3].

In this study, we conduct the design, synthesis, structural confirmation and carbonic anhydrase inhibition studies on (E)-2-(1-(4-cyanophenyl)ethylidene)-N-(2-fluoro-4-sulfamoylphenyl)hydrazine-1-carbothioamide (compound **1**) based on the structure of SLC-0111. SLC-0111 is a selective and potent CA inhibitor that has successfully completed Phase I clinical trials in patients with advanced solid tumors [4,5].

Scheme 2. Design of Compound 1

To confirm the thione-thiol tautomerism and geometrical isomerism of compound **1**, theoretical IR and bond distance were predicted with computational methods. Subsequently, experimental IR and single X-ray studies were conducted, and the results were compared with the theoretical data, both confirming the presence of thione form and *E* isomerism.

Materials and Methods

Materials

4-acetylbenzotrile, *para*-toluenesulfonic acid and ethanol were procured commercially. *N*-(2-fluoro-4-sulfamoylphenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamide was prepared as reported by Trawally and coworkers [6]. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) was conducted on 0.2 mm thick ready-made silica gel F-254 (Merck) aluminum plates (20 × 20 cm), and the spots were visualized under ultraviolet light. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded as thin KBr pellets using a Shimadzu IRAffinity-1 FTIR Spectrophotometer. The theoretical IR spectrum was predicted using Schrödinger package (v2023-2; Schrödinger, Inc., New York).

Methods

Chemistry: Synthesis of (E)-2-(1-(4-cyanophenyl)ethylidene)-N-(2-fluoro-4-sulfamoylphenyl)hydrazine-1-carbothioamide (Compound 1)

Compound **1** was prepared from a condensation reaction of *N*-(2-fluoro-4-sulfamoylphenyl)hydrazinecarbothioamide and 4-acetylbenzotrile at equimolar concentration in methanol, under reflux and in the presence of *para*-toluenesulfonic acid (*p*TSOH) (Scheme 2) [6]. The completion of the reaction was determined with TLC visualization. The reaction mixture was cooled down and the precipitate was filtered out, dried and recrystallized from ethanol to obtain the pure compound as a yellow powder.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of Compound 1

Single X-ray diffraction analyses

Compound **1** was crystallized using slow evaporation. For single-crystal X-ray analysis, the crystal was mounted on a micromount and attached to a goniometer head on a Bruker D8 VENTURE diffractometer equipped with a PHOTON100 detector. The measurements were performed using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) with 1.0° of Ω and Φ rotation frames at room temperature. The structure was solved and refined using SHELXS-1997 [7].

Carbonic anhydrase inhibition

Using a stopped-flow device (SX.18MV-R Applied Photophysics model), compound **1** and SLC-0111 were tested in enzyme inhibition assays against the pharmaceutically important hCA I, hCA II, hCA IX and hCA XII as reported in literature [8].

Results and Conclusions

The preparation compound **1** was initially attempted without a catalyst, however, the obtained product showed the presence of geometrical isomers. The use of the *p*TSOH catalyst resulted in the production of *E* isomer with a yield of 80%.

The theoretical IR data revealed the characteristic bands for the thiosemicarbazone compound **1**. These bands include the N-H stretching vibrations which were observed at $3649, 3574 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the cyano

C≡N stretching vibration which was observed at 2349 cm⁻¹, the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of S=O which were respectively observed at 1342, 1157 cm⁻¹ and the thiocarbonyl C=S which was observed at 1229 cm⁻¹ (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Theoretical IR and crystal structure of compound **1**

Similar to the theoretical prediction, the experimental IR data revealed that the N-H stretching vibrations were observed at 3288, 3255 cm⁻¹, the cyano C≡N stretching vibration was observed at 2233 cm⁻¹, the asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of S=O were respectively observed at 1342, 1157 cm⁻¹ and the thiocarbonyl C=S was observed at 1224 cm⁻¹ (Figure 2). As demonstrated in Scheme 1, compound **1** may undergo thione-thiol tautomerism; however, as confirmed by the experimental IR data, the presence of the C=S band with no characteristic SH-related peak between 2500 – 2800 cm⁻¹ is an indication that compound **1** is in its thione form [9].

Figure 2. Experimental IR and crystal structure of compound **1**

Furthermore, single X-ray studies were conducted to further confirm the thione-thiol tautomerism and geometrical isomerism of compound **1**. The obtained data revealed that compound **1** exhibits trans (*E*) configuration and it is in thione state (Figure 3). In addition, the results revealed that the experimental bond lengths are comparable to the theoretical calculated bond lengths as summarized in Table 1. The bond length of S1–C10, measured as 1.676 Å, is shorter than the bond length of S2–C16, measured as

1.760 Å. This confirms that the S1–C10 is a sp² hybridized bond and that compound **1** is present in the thione form.

Figure 2. Crystal structure of compound **1** illustrated with thermal ellipsoids drawn at 50% probability to show the spatial arrangement of the atoms.

Table 1. Theoretical and experimental bond lengths of compound **1**

Bond Length/Type	Theoretical (Å)	Experimental (Å)
O1-S2	1.494	1.437
S2-C16	1.841	1.760
S2-N5	1.574	1.616
S1-C10	1.669	1.676
N4-C10	1.361	1.345
N3-C10	1.400	1.336
N2-N3	1.348	1.390
N2-C8	1.289	1.262

In addition, compound **1** and SLC-0111 were tested for their hCA inhibition against hCA I, II, IX and XII. The result of the assay is summarized in Figure 4. Compound **1** exhibited inhibition constant K_i values of 36.0, 5.7, 29.5 and 7.0 nM, against hCA I, II, IX and XII, respectively, showing that compound **1** is more potent against hCA I, II and IX when compared to the reference SLC-0111. However, compound **1** lacks selectivity as it strongly inhibits all the four isoenzymes.

Figure 3. hCA inhibition of compound 1 and SLC-0111

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